

DICKSON ADOM

Department of Educational Innovations in Science and Technology, KNUST, Kumasi, Ghana.

CONTACT

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ONLINE PROFILE LINKS:

https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Dickson_Adom (RESEARCHGATE)

<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=uNWIlQMAAAAJ&hl=en> (GOOGLE SCHOLAR)

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0559-4173> (ORCID)

https://figshare.com/authors/DICKSON_ADOM/4032767 (FIGSHARE)

https://www.growkudos.com/profile/dickson_adom (KUDOS)

https://ezinearticles.com/expert/Dickson_Adom/2315408 (EZINES)

<https://www.linkedin.com/in/dickson-adom-274007ab?originalSubdomain=gh> (LINKEDIN)

<https://webapps.knust.edu.gh/staff/dirsearch/profile/summary/fe9eab39160e.html> (KNUST)

<https://atmenson.academia.edu/DICKSONADOM> (ACADEMIA)

<https://mobile.twitter.com/dickson28771711> (TWITTER)

<https://www.webofscience.com/wos/author/record/J-7934-2016> (WEB OF SCIENCE)

ResearcherID: J-7934-2016

Scopus Author ID: 57206656159

Loop profile: 1360592

SciProfiles: 406819

ACADEMIC DEGREES

- PhD in African Art and Culture (*Grade A*)- KNUST - November 2018
- Post Graduate Diploma in Education (*Distinction*) UEW - December 2011
- MA African Art and Culture (*Grade A*) KNUST - November 2009
- BA Integrated Rural Art and Industry (*First Class*) KNUST– May 2006
- Pyramids of Giza: Ancient Egyptian Art and Archaeology (Certificate)- December 2020 (Department of Archaeology, Harvard University, U.S.)
- African Art History (Certificate)- FPLI-Academia Luso Italiana, Lda, Italy, December,2021.
- Africa in Emerging Economies (Certificate) – March 2021 (School of Business, Harvard University, U.S.)
- Post Doctoral Research in African Art and Culture- December 2020 (University of Liepzig, Germany)
- Facilitating Online (Certificate)- November 2020 (University of Cape Town, South Africa)
- Editorial Workflow in OJS 3- June 2020 (Simon Fraser University, Canada)

RESEARCH AREAS

Place Identity History, African Art History, Cultural Anthropology, Cultural Enterprises, Indigenous Knowledge Systems, Community Engagement, Museum Studies, African Art, TEK for Nature Conservation and Environmental Sustainability, Cultural Education, TVET Education, Visual Arts Education

PROFILE INFORMATION

Dr. Dickson Adom is a researcher in the pluridisciplinary fields of Place Identity History, African Art, Art Installations, and Cultural Anthropology for Biodiversity Conservation, Ethno-cultural medicine, Environmental Sustainability, Heritage Sites Conservation. He is an expert in the use of traditional knowledge systems and community engagement strategies in nature conservation projects.

CITATION COUNTS

- Citations- 2157
- H-index- 18

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ACADEMIC POSITIONS

Lecturer & Examinations Officer

RESEARCHGATE ACHIEVEMENT

Research Interest Score- 9, 978 (Higher than 99% of researchers on ResearchGate).

ONLINE VISIBILITY LINKS:

YOUTUBE LINKS TO PRESENTATIONS:

Watch " Ideation Contest 2021, Welcome address from one of the International Judges, Dr. Dickson Adom, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Ghana " on YouTube Link:

https://youtu.be/_s11-zrpa1k

Watch "Multimodal Delivery Platforms in the Post Pandemic Era: Universal Design for Learning Framework" by Dr. Dickson Adom, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Ghana" on YouTube Link:

<https://youtu.be/VjELjNMUnAo>

Watch "Critical and Constructive Review by Dr. Dickson Adom, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Ghana" on YouTube Link:

<https://youtu.be/tP8HjVj4nyM>

FACEBOOK LINKS TO PRESENTATIONS:

Watch "Museum sector of Ghana requires community engagement", by Dr. Dickson Adom, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Ghana" on Facebook Link:

TEACHING (COURSES)

- **Museum Studies** (Doctor of Philosophy and Master of Philosophy Students in African Art and Culture)
- **History of African Art** (Doctor of Philosophy and Master of Philosophy Students in African Art and Culture)
- **Socio-Politics of African Art** (Master of Philosophy Students in African Art and Culture)
- **Aesthetics and Criticism** (Doctor of Philosophy and Master of Philosophy Students in African Art and Culture/ Doctor of Philosophy and Master of Philosophy Art Education)
- **Art Education Studio Practice** (Master of Art in Art Education)
- **Research Methods** (Doctor of Philosophy and Master of Philosophy Students in African Art and Culture)
- **History of Global Art** (Undergraduate students in Faculty of Art)
- **Introduction to African Art and Culture** (Undergraduate students in Faculty of Art)
- **Foundations of Social Studies and TVET** (Undergraduate Students in the Faculty of Educational Studies)

UNIVERSITY SERVICE ACTIVITIES

1. Appointed as KNUST Representative on the Research Pillar of the African Centre for Career Enhancement & Skills Support (A program run between the University of Leipzig, Germany and the Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology) - October 2020
2. Appointed as a member of the 3-member committee to select awardees of the ACCESS (K.N.U.S.T./University of Leipzig, Germany) virtual short-term scholarship for October 2021-December 2021
3. Appointed as a member of the College of Art and Built Environment Examination Audit Committee, July 2021
4. Appointed as Examinations Officer, Department of Educational Innovations in Science and Technology, KNUST, November 2022
5. Appointed as a member of the Faculty of Educational Studies Journal Committee, November 2020
6. Appointed as GESI Proposal Committee Member, October 2022
7. Appointed as a member of the Departmental Accreditation Committee, November 2020
8. Appointed by the Faculty of Educational Studies to be trained as Universal Design for Learning master trainer for K.N.U.S.T. and Affiliate Colleges of Education, September 2021

<https://m.facebook.com/ANOghana/videos/the-museum-sector-of-ghana-requires-intentional-coommunity-engagement-and-a-stead/574898113824614/>

LINKS TO NEWS ITEMS:

African Universities Resolve To Achieve CESA (2016-2025) In Cairo

<https://www.modernghana.com/amp/news/945321/african-universities-resolve-to-achieve-cesa-2016-2025-in.html>

Ghana appoints experts to draw up 'radical' new plan for museums and monuments

<https://www.theartnewspaper.com/2020/10/29/ghana-appoints-experts-to-draw-up-radical-new-plan-for-museums-and-monuments>

Dietary Taboos as a means of ethnic and place identity of the Bono people of Ghana

<https://www.culturalencyclopaedia.org/dietary-taboos-asa-means-of-ethnic-and-place-identity-of-the-bono-people-of-ghana-indirect-cultural>

Dr. Dickson Adom, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology inducted into the prestigious fraternity of young scientists in Ghana, The Ghana Young Academy

<https://www.ghanayoungacademy.org/member-profile-dr-dickson-adom/>

Zervas Art Ghana established by Dr. Dickson Adom, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Ghana to boost the study of Art and Culture in the country

<https://zervas-art.com/clubsfederation/zervas-art-club-in-ghana/>

Dr. Dickson Adom, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology establishes the Journal of Innovations in Art and Culture for Nature Conservation and Environmental Sustainability

<https://journals.adompublications.com/index.php/j>

9. Appointed as a teaching assessor for five Master of Philosophy in Educational Leadership Science candidates- August 14, 2021

10. Appointed as a member of the 2-member committee by the Department of Educational Innovations in Science and Technology to review the B. ED. Art and Technology Education programme, May 2021

11. Appointed as an Internal Examiner for 2 Ph. D. Candidates, five MPhil candidates and supervised one graduated MPhil candidate while currently supervising 5 PhD students and 3 MPhil students in the Department of Educational Innovations in Science and Technology/Department of Painting and Sculpture- Since October, 2021

12. Appointed as a fellow for the University Hall, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, October 2020

13. Appointed as the Chairman for the Journal Development Committee of Educational Innovations in Science and Technology Department, K.N.U.S.T., February 2022

14. Appointed as a member of the KNUST 70th Anniversary Exhibition CABE Committee. February, 2022

15. Appointed as a member of the Department Programmes Accreditation Committee, November 2022

16. Appointed as a member of the Bachelor of Art and Technology Curriculum Review Committee, April 2022

17. Appointed as a member of the Faculty of Educational Studies Programmes Accreditation Committee, December 2022

18. Appointed as Co-Chair for the Faculty of Educational Studies Doctoral Conference, January 2022

NATIONAL SERVICE SACTIVITIES

1. Appointed by His Excellency, Nana Addo Danquah Akuffo Addo as a member of the Presidential Committee on Future of Ghana's Museums and Cultural Heritage- October 19, 2020
2. Inducted as a member of the Ghana Young Academy, March 5, 2021
3. Chief Examiner for General Knowledge in Art (Ghana Teacher Licensure Examination)- National Teaching Council, Ministry of Education, Ghana
4. Chief Examiner and Course Lead, Foundations of Social Studies and TVET (Colleges of Education affiliated to KNUST)
5. WAEC Itinerant Examiner for Senior High School Examinations
6. Facilitator, Professional Development Webinar on Research Article Writing in Art, Art Teachers' Association of Ghana, August 2020
7. Principal Investigator, Capacity building training workshop in cultural and traditional craft enterprises in the Sekyere-East District- Financed by DAAD, Germany- 1, 800 Euros

8. Research Lead, Sexual Harassment Baseline Survey in the 5 affiliated Colleges of Education, courtesy the Ghana Tertiary Education Commission (GTEC) and Transforming Teaching, Education and Learning (T-TEL) and funded by the Mastercard Foundation, October 2022
9. Academic Judge, GESI Challenge for the 5 affiliated Colleges of Education, courtesy the Ghana Tertiary Education Commission (GTEC) and Transforming Teaching, Education and Learning (T-TEL) and funded by the Mastercard Foundation, December 2022
10. Facilitator, GESI Capacity Building Workshop for the 5 affiliated Colleges of Education, courtesy the Ghana Tertiary Education Commission (GTEC) and Transforming Teaching, Education and Learning (T-TEL) and funded by the Mastercard Foundation, November 2022
11. Reesearch & Technical Lead, Fidelity of Implementation (FOI) Research Project on the Bachelor of Education Programme in the 46 Colleges of Education in Ghana, Ghana Tertiary Education Commission (GTEC), April 2022
12. Academic Publisher, Adom Series Publications Limited, June 2022

INTERNATIONAL SERVICE SACTIVITIES

1. Appointed as the country president and ambassador for Zervas National Art Clubs in Ghana by the Club for UNESCO of Art and Letters in Achaia & Patras, Greece- 12th July, 2021
2. Extraordinary Researcher Position, School of Economic Sciences, North-West University, South Africa, January 2019-December 2021
3. International Advisory Council Member, Philippine Association of Research Practitioners, Educators and Statistical Software Users, Pangasinan, Philippines
4. Assessor for Grants and Promotions, National Research Foundation, South Africa, January 2020-Present
5. Member of International Panel, Innoculture Ideation Contest 2021, India and Singapore (ERODE Engineering College), June 2021
6. Panelist, Research Integrity with the Pillars of Academia, Editage Insights, September 2022
7. Panel Member, Questions and Answer Session on Research Idea Conceptualization, Research Roadmap Club, JFP Publishers, South Africa, 27th August, 2021
8. Paper Evaluator for Best Thesis Awards, Graduate Research Public Defense, School of Advanced Studies, Pangasinan State University, Phillipines, August 2022
9. Ghanaian Committee Member, First Aswan Festival for African Music and Song, Aswan, Egypt, November 2020

10. Guest Speaker, Q & A Session of Peer Review Webinar, Papyrus Bootcamp: Writing Peer Review Based on the Standards of Web of Science, Mindanao State University, Phillipines, December 2021
11. Review Panelist, 2nd In-House Research and Extension Proposal Review, Centre for History, Culture, Arts, Language and Innovative Education, Pangasinan State University, Phillipines, October 2021
12. Plenary Speaker, 2022 International Conference on Research in Educational Sciences, Mindanao State University, Phillipines, May 2022
13. Keynote Speaker, PARESSU Inc., Phillipines, ASEAN Multidisciplinary Conference, March 2021
14. Public Lecture on Writing Scholarly Papers, Swedish Iraqi Studies Network, Lund University, Sweden, January 2021
15. Conference Session Chair & Organizing Committee Member, ICETIS 2021, Universiti Malaysia Kelantan (UMK), Malaysia, December 2021
16. Conference Session Chair, ASEAN Multidisciplinary Conference, PARESSU Inc., Phillipines, November 2021
17. Jury Member, Project Proposal Review, AI Application for Special Children, Industry 4.0 World Resources Webinar, December 2022
18. Certified Academic Mentor, Publons Academy, Switzerland, May 2020

Awards

1. World Federation of Zervas Art Clubs Award & The Club for UNESCO of ART & LETTERS in Achaia Award, Greece for the establishment of the Scientific, Cultural and Artistic Organization 'Zervas Art Clubs in Ghana' – 12th July, 2021
2. Young Scientist Award 2019, Regional Universities Forum for Capacity Building in Science, Innovations and Technology) for the development of an innovative traditional conservation strategy for Ghana's biodiversity with a cash price of 2000 USD, December 2019
3. CABE Excellence Awards. Most promising Senior Member- 1st Runner Up (2020/2021 Academic Year), November 2021
4. #1 Best Social Sciences/Anthropology Research Scientist in KNUST and #2 Best Anthropology Research Scientist (AD Scientific Index)
5. Short Term Post-Doctoral Research Award, ACCESS-KNUST & University of Leipzig, Germany, October 2020

RESEARCH/TRAVEL GRANTS

1. Chapter on 'Community Engagement and Museums' for the National/Presidential Museum and Cultural Heritage Committee Report- 2000

USD

2. British Academy Travel Grant, Research Writing Retreat, University of Ghana, December 2019- 900 EUROS

3. Association of African Universities Conference Travel Grant, November 2019- 1500 USD

4. Getty Foundation Travel Grant, CIHA World Congress, February 2020- 6000 USD

5. Beneficiary of North-West University, South Africa IREA-program (Institutional Research Excellence Award-program) for Extraordinary Researcher Position in the School of Economic Sciences- 2019-2021S

6. Harvard X Scholarship Award (Africa Live! Entrepreneurship in Emerging Communities)- Harvard University and Africa Live Scholarship Secretariat, December 2020-February 2021- 1080 USD

7. Post Doctoral Scholarship Grant- DAAD with funding from the Federal Ministry of Economic Cooperation and Development, Germany- with grant number-ACCESS 2020 (17250729)- 1, 800 EUROS

8. GESI Project in 5 Colleges of Education affiliated to KNUST (GESI capacity building workshop, GESI Challenge, and Sexual Harrassment Baseline Survey)- October 2022- 15,100 USD by Mastercard Foundation/T-TEL/GTEC

RESEARCH AND PUBLICATION

Journal Articles

2022

1. **Adom, D.** (2022). Personal Reflection on Practice as a Basic and Senior High School Teacher Using Gibbs Reflective Model: Universal Design for Learning (UDL) in Focus. *REACH: Journal of Inclusive Education in Ireland*, 35(1): 63-82

2. Thulla, P.F.Y., Moriba, S., **Adom, D.** & Mensah-Gborie, M.N.S. (2022). The Rate of Reading Poverty After the COVID- 19 Pandemic School Shutdown and Specific Intervention Strategies for Lower Primary School Pupils in the Southern Province and Western Area of Sierra Leone. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 13, 689-696. DOI: 10.17507/jltr.1304.01.
3. Tetteh, N., Ali Dansieh, S. & **Adom, D.** (2022). Imagery of Dagaare and Waala proverbs: Visual eisegesis. *Cogent Arts and Humanities*, 9, 1-26. 10.1080/23311983.2022.2086513
4. **Adom, D.**, Chukwuere, J., Addo, I., Agyei, E. & Thulla, P.F.Y. (2022). African Proverbs for Cultural Education: A Step towards Digital Archiving. *Journal of History, Culture and Art Research*, 10(4): 44-59.
5. **Adom, D.**, Nyadu-Addo, R. & Kquofi, S. (2022). Capacity building in cultural and traditional craft enterprises for ecotourism development in the Sekyere Kumawu district of Ghana. *Journal of Urban Culture Research*, 23(1): 44-78.
6. **Adom, D.** (2022). Catch them young: Children as messengers of indigenous ecological knowledge for biodiversity conservation in Ghana. *Journal of Wildlife and Biodiversity*, 6(3): 12-25. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6522108>
7. **Adom, D.** & Adu-Mensah, J. (2022). Traditional mortuary rites culture among the Akans of Ghana. *Academia Letters*, Article 4678 <https://doi.org/10.20935/AL4678>
8. Asamoah, S., **Adom, D.**, Kquofi, S. & Nyadu-Addo, R. (2022). Recycled Art from Plastic Waste for Environmental Sustainability and Aesthetics in Ghana. *Research Journal in Advanced Humanities*, 3(1), 23-46.
9. Brewu, J., Kquofi, S., **Adom, D.**, Bodjawah, E. & Adu-Agyem, J. (2022). The Historical Development, Cultural and Aesthetic Significance of Akan Musical Artform (Ebibindwom) in the Liturgy of the Methodist Church Ghana. *Asian Research Journal of Arts & Social Sciences*, 17, 10-20.
10. Owusu, E. K., **Adom, D.** & Adu-Agyem, J. (2022). Internal quality assurance in health training institutions: The case of selected physician assistant training institutions in Bono East and Ahafo Regions. *Pangasinan State University's Journal of Advanced Studies*, 5(1): 1-19.
11. Asamoah, S. P., **Adom, D.** & Kushiator, G. (2022). Iconographic analysis of the masterpieces of the British-Ghanaian mixed media artist, Godfried Donkor. *Journal of Arts and Humanities*, 10(11), 19-27.
12. **Adom, D.**, Chukwuere, J. E., Addo, I. A., Agyei, E. T. & Thulla, P.F.Y. (2022). African proverbs for cultural education: A step towards digital archiving. *Journal of History, Culture and Art Research*, 10(4): 44-59.
13. Kquofi, S., Kusi, T., **Adom, D.**, Bodjawah, E. & Glover, R. (2022). Historical and socio-cultural significance of the Ahenema Mpaboa in the Asante royal regalia. *Journal of Education, Culture, and Society*, 7(3):119-128 DOI: 10.11648/j..ijecs.20220703.11

2021

14. **Adom, D.**, Adu Mensah, J. & Kquofi, S. (2021). COVID-19 Private Burials with 25 Persons in the Lens of the Mortuary Rites Culture in Ghana. *African Identities* <https://doi.org/10.1080/14725843.2021.1947188>
15. Tankpara, P., **Adom, D.** & Adu-Agyem, J. (2021). The State of Quality Assurance Policies in Nursing and Midwifery Training Colleges in the Upper West Region of Ghana. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, 10(2): 455-464.
16. Essel, H. B., Dimitros, V., **Adom, D.** & Tachie-Menson, A. (2021). Transforming Higher Education in Ghana in Times of Disruption: Flexible Learning in Rural Communities with High Latency Internet Connectivity. *Journal of Enterprising Communities, People and Places in Global Economy*, DOI: 10.1108/JEC.08.2020.0151
17. **Adom, D.**, Adu Mensah, J. & Osei, M. (2021). The Psychological Distress and Mental Health Disorders from COVID-19 Stigmatization in Ghana. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 4, 100186
18. Chukwuere, P. C., Chukwuere, J. E. & **Adom, D.** (2021). The psychosocial effects of social media cyberbullying on students in selected African countries. *Acta Informatica Malaysia* 5(2): 62-70.
19. **Adom, D.** (2021). The Sustainability of the Science in the Productive Cultural Instruments of African Ancestors for Natural Resource Management. *Journal of African Art and Culture*, 5(1): 45-71.

20. **Adom, D.** (2021). Writing Scholarly Papers: A Window from my Experiences. *ASEAN Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 8(1): 1-9.
21. **Adom, D.** (2021). Lead authorship position in published articles for thesis: The student versus the supervisor. *Academic Letters*, Article 3421. <https://doi.org/10.20935/AL3421>
22. Wemegah, I., Danso, D. K., & **Adom, D.** (2021). Socio-cultural and economic importance of Kete weaving in Agortime traditional area, Ghana. *Asian Research Journal of Arts & Social Sciences*, 15(1): 43-53.
23. **Adom, D.**, Sharma, E., Sharma, S. & Agyei, I. (2021). Teaching strategies, school environment, and culture: Drivers of Creative pedagogy in Ghanaian schools. *Studies in Learning and Teaching*, 2(2): 12-25.
24. Gouthami, V., Amitha B. K. Hyder, **Adom, D.**, & Aneesh, C. (2021). Ethnoecology of wild honey collection by Kadar ethnic community endemic to Western Ghats. *International Journal of Scientific Research*, 12(10): 43255-43262.
25. Akpem, B., Tetteh, N. A. & **Adom, D.** (2021). Influence of teacher professional development on teaching and learning in public Technical Institutes in the Upper West Region of Ghana. *Journal of Education, Society and Behavioural Science*, 34(12): 13-31.
26. Osei, M., **Adom, D.**, Twene, A. & Tetteh, N. A. (2021). Burnout syndrome during the COVID-19 pandemic among visual art teachers in Ghana. *Studies in Learning and Teaching*, 2(3): 115-129.
27. Asamoah, S. P., **Adom, D.**, Adu-Agyem, J. & Padditey, E. (2021). Our encounter with the genius Ghanaian contemporary painter, Jonathan Kwegyir Aggrey. *ADRRJ Journal of Arts and Social Sciences*, 18(3): 226-243.
28. Agbezuge, M. A., Danso, D.K. & **Adom, D.** (2021). General attitudes, cultural significance and health risks associated with body arts among Ewe youth in the Volta Region of Ghana. *Art and Design Review*, 10(1): 1-17.

2020

29. **Adom, D.**, Daitey, S. T., Yarney, L. & Fening, P. A. (2020). Breaking the Culture-Specific Silence of Women Glass Bead Makers in Ghana: Towards an Empowerment. *Safety and Health at Work*, 11(4): 450-457 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.shaw.2020.08.002>
30. **Adom, D.** & Boamah, D. A. (2020). Local Attitudes toward the Cultural Seasonal Hunting Bans in Ghana's Bomfobiri Wildlife Sanctuary: Implications for Sustainable Wildlife Management and Tourism. *Global Ecology and Conservation*, 24 (e01243): 113
31. **Adom, D.**, Chukweure, J. & Osei, M. (2020). Review: Academic Stress among Faculty and Student in Higher Institutions. *Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 28(2): 1055-1064
32. **Adom, D.**, Adu-Mensah, J. & Appiah, S. P. (2020). Hand-to-Mouth Work Culture and the COVID-19 Lockdown Restrictions: Experiences of Selected Informal Sector Workers in Kumasi, Ghana. *Research Journal in Advanced Humanities*, 1(2): 45-64
33. **Adom, D.** (2020). Cultural and Educational Implications of COVID-19 in Ghana. *International and Multidisciplinary Journal of Social Sciences* 9(3): 1-27.
34. Adom, D., Adu-Mensah, J. & Dake, D. A. (2020). Test, Measurement, and Evaluation: Understanding and Use of the Concepts in Education. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, 9(1): 109-119
35. **Adom, D.**, Abdolresa, R. F., Sajjadi, J. & Sedighi, S. (2020). Factors influencing Tourism Space Commodification in Iran. *Journal of Tourismology*, 6(2): 155-183.
36. Koranteng, J., Morro, I. & **Adom, D.** (2020). Constructivist Teaching Strategies for Graphic Design Education in Selected Senior High Schools in Ghana. *Journal of African Art Education*, 1(2): 21-43.
37. **Adom, D.**, Osei, M. & Adu-Agyem, J. (2020). From Ghanaian Modernist Painting Genre to Contemporary Functionality: A Spotlight on Samuel Prophask Asamoah. *Journal of Urban Culture Research*, 21(1): 61-89.
38. **Adom, D.** (2020). Are the Humanities really 'A Wheel Turning Nothing' in the Global Fight against the COVID-19 Pandemic? *Nairobi Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 4(4): 1-8 .
39. **Adom, D.**, Essel, H. B. & Chukwuere, J. (2020). The State of Academic Stress in the Higher Institutions of Ghana: The Way Forward. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 8(2): 321-331
40. **Adom, D.**, Sawicka, B., Umachandran, K. & Ziarati, P. (2020). Effective Approaches in Ensuring the Active Involvement of Local People in Biodiversity Conservation Projects. *International Journal of Basic & Applied Sciences*, 20(2): 17-31

41. Manu, G., Howard, E. K., **Adom, D.** & Agyemang, O. (2020). Textile Installation Inspired by Cubism for Biodiversity Sustainability Education. *Journal of Urban Culture Research*, 20(1): 55-68

2019

42. **Adom, D.** (2019). The Place and Voice of Local People, Culture, and Traditions: A Catalyst for Ecotourism Development in Rural Communities in Ghana. *Scientific African*, 6 (e00184): 1-22
43. **Adom, D.** (2019). Dietary Taboos as a Means of Ethnic and Place Identity of the Bono People of Ghana: Indirect Cultural Practices for the Conservation of Fauna Species. *International Journal of Conservation Science*, 10(4): 733-748
44. **Adom, D.**, Chukwuere, J., Dake, D. A. & Newton, J. P. (2019). Problem Learners in Selected Elementary Schools in Ghana: Toward Understanding, Prevention and Action. *Asia-Pacific Research Journal of Early Childhood Education*, 13(1): 107-129
45. **Adom, D.**, Umachandran, K., Boamah, D. A., Ziarati, P. & Sawicka, B. (2019). The Concept, State, Roles and Management of Protected Areas in Ghana: A Review. *Acta Scientific Agriculture*, 3(1): 68-76
46. **Adom, D.**, Appiah, P. S. & Yarney, L. (2019). A Return to the Ghanaian Cultural Values of Closed Season in Ghana's Artisanal Marine Fishing: An Essential Means of Restoring Small Pelagic Stocks. *Rev. Syst. Ecol. Res.*, 21(3): 95-110
47. Danso, D. K., **Adom, D.**, Eshun, F. S. & Adamtey, S. (2019). Ghanaian Cultural Values and their Foreign Influence: A Spotlight on Clothing. *Journal of Fashion Technology & Textile Engineering*, 7(1): 1-8
48. **Adom, D.** (2019). Good Management Practices for Agricultural Crops: A Mini Review. *Acta Scientific Agriculture*, 3(6): 8-11
49. **Adom, D.**, Umachandran, K., Ziarati, P., Sawicka, B. & Appiah, P. S. (2019). The Concept of Biodiversity and Its Relevance to Mankind: A Short Review. *Journal of Agriculture and Sustainability*, 12(2): 219-231
50. Chukweure, J., **Adom, D.** & Gorejena, K. (2019). Towards an Indigenous Crowdfunding Framework: A New Guide for Entrepreneurship Funding in Developing Countries. *Gender and Behaviour*, 17(12): 12742-12755

BOOK CHAPTERS

1. Sawicka, B., Aslan, I., Corte, V., Periasamy, A., Krishnamurthy, S., Mohammed, A., Said, M., Saravanan, P., Del Gaudio, G., **Adom, D.**, Sawicki, B., Nevola, G., Hanchate, D. & Umachandran, K. (2022). The coronavirus global pandemic and its impacts on society. *Coronavirus Drug Discovery*, Elsevier Inc. DOI: 10.1016/B978-0-323-85156-5.00037-7
2. Sawicka, B., Ziarati, P., Behmanesh, M., Skiba, D. & **Adom, D.** (2022). Plants sources of vitamins against SARS-CoV-2. *Coronavirus Drug Discovery*, Elsevier Inc. DOI: 10.1016/B978-0-323-95574-4.00011-1.
3. **Adom, D.** & Twene, A. (2022). Social media research writing, dissemination, and publication. IN: A-Z of social media research methods. South Africa: Jozac Publishers ISBN: 978-0-6397-1238-3
4. **Adom, D.** (2021). Community Engagement and Ghana's Museums and Cultural Heritage. IN *Presidential Committee's Report on Ghana's Museums and Cultural Heritage*. London: Bolton & Quinn's Publishers.
5. **Adom, D.**, Appiah, P. S. & Krishnappa, M. K. (2020). *The Chemical Constituents, AntiInflammatory, Anti-Oxidant and Ethnomedicinal Properties of Aloe barbadensis* IN *Ethnomedicinal Plant Use and Practice in Traditional Medicine*. U.S.A.: IGI Global DOI: 10.4018/978-1-6684-3546-5.ch024.
6. **Adom, D.** & Aravind, V. R. (2019). *Application of Educational Technology to Teaching and Learning in the 20th and 21st Centuries* IN *History of Educational Technology (20th & 21st Centuries)*. 2019, pp. 41-53, Malaysia: ALNIL Enterprise, ISBN: 978-967-168462-7
7. **Adom, D.** & Ferdinand-James, D. S. (2019). Historical Overview of Educational Technology in the *20th and 21st Centuries* IN *History of Educational Technology*. Malaysia: ALNIL Enterprise. ISBN: 978-967-16846-2-7

8. Adetunji, C. O., Egbuna, C., Tijani, H., **Adom, D.** & Al-Ani, L. (2019). *Homemade Preparations of Natural Biopesticides and Applications*. IN *Natural Remedies for Pest, Disease and Weed Control*. UK: Elsevier Publisher. ISBN: 9780128193044
9. Sawicka, B., Skiba, D., Umachandran, K. & **Adom, D.** (2020). *Alternative and New Plants*. IN *Traditional Systems of Medicine*. U. K.: Elsevier Publishers, Inc.

EDITED BOOKS

1. Panda, P., Padmanaban, S., Subudhi, C. & **Adom, D.** (2022). *COVID-19: Impacts on Health, Economy and Society*. Neelkamal Publisher ISBN: 978-93-90897-38-4
2. Chukwuere, J., **Adom, D.** & Chukwuere, P. C. (2022). *A-Z of Social Media Research Methods*. South Africa: Jozac Publishers ISBN: 978-0-6397-1238-3
3. Chukwuere, J., **Adom, D.** & Umachandran, K. (2022). *ICETIS 2022 Proceedings*. South Africa: Jozac Publishers
<https://doi.org/10.57040/icetis.vi.22>
4. **Adom, D.**, Chukwuere, J. E. & Umachandran, K. (2021). *Innovations in Teaching and Learning in the COVID-19 Crisis*. Mahikeng, South Africa: Jozac Publishers, ISBN: 9781-991215-93-2
5. **Adom, D.** (Ed.), Mumma, C. (2021). *Thesis writing: A practical guide for students and supervisors*. U. K. & Kenya: Royallite Publishers ISBN: 9789914401936

MONOGRAPH

1. **Adom, D.** (2022). *Traditional Biodiversity Conservation Strategy for Ghana*. South Africa: Jozac Publishers ISBN: 978-0-620-99745-4

CONFERENCE PAPERS

1. **Adom, D.** (2022). *Multimodal Delivery Approaches in the Post-Pandemic Era: The Universal Design for Learning Framework*. Plenary Speech in Conference Proceedings for the International Conference on Research in Educational Sciences, Philippines Themed 'Redesigning the educational system in alternative delivery platforms: Moving towards post pandemic', 29-31 May, 2022., College of Education, Mindanao State University, Philippines, pp. 45-49.
2. Owusu, E. K. & **Adom, D.** (2022). *Postpartum anaemia among lactating mothers in the Techiman municipality, Ghana: Prevalence, cultural barriers and mitigating strategies*. World Women Conference-IV. Mata Sundri College of Women, University of Delhi in partnership with the Institute of Economic Development and Social Research, Turkey, March 8-9, 2022 ISBN: 978-625-7464-80-2, pp. 654-686.
3. **Adom, D.** (2022). *Asante Kente: A home craft and a cultural symbol of unconditional hospitality for migrant art genres and cultures*. 35th CIHA World Congress, Sao Paulo, Brazil, January 13-30, 2022.
4. **Adom, D.** & **Adom, D.** (2021). *Resource co-management: Incorporating TEK into resource management frameworks*. *ICETIS 2021 Conference Proceedings- Arts and Humanities Session*, Mahikeng, South Africa

TEXTBOOKS

1. **Adom, D.** & Agyeman, O. (2019). *Picture Making for Senior High Schools*. Kumasi: Adom Series Publications Limited.
2. **Adom, D.** (2019). *Leatherwork for Senior High Schools*. Kumasi: Adom Series Publications Limited
3. **Adom, D.** (2020). *General Knowledge in Art for Senior High Schools*. Kumasi: Adom Series Publications Limited

RESEARCH COLLABORATIONS (INSTITUTIONAL, NATIONAL & INTERNATIONAL)

Institutional Collaborations - KNUST (Disciplinary)	Institutional Collaborations - KNUST (Inter, cross and multi Disciplinary)	Institutional Collaborations-National (Inter, cross and multi Disciplinary)	Institutional Collaborations-Internatiional (Inter, cross and multi Disciplinary)
<p>Essel, H. B. (Educational Innovations, KNUST, Ghana)</p> <p>Osei, M. (Educational Innovations, KNUST, Ghana)</p> <p>Adu-Agyem, J. (Educational Innovations, KNUST, Ghana)</p> <p>Kusi, T. (Educational Innovations, KNUST, Ghana)</p> <p>Kquofi, S. (Educational Innovations, KNUST, Ghana)</p> <p>Dake, D. A. (Educational Innovations, KNUST, Ghana)</p> <p>Tachie-Menson, A. (Educational Innovations, KNUST, Ghana)</p> <p>Tankpara, P. (Educational Innovations,</p>	<p>Howard, E. K. (Industrial Art, KNUST, Ghana)</p> <p>Agyemang, O. (Painting & SCulpture, KNUST, Ghana)</p> <p>Nyadu-Addo, R. (Publishing Studies, KNUST, Ghana)</p> <p>Koranteng, J. (Communications Design, KNUST, Ghana)</p> <p>Morro, I. (Communications Design, KNUST, Ghana)</p> <p>Kushiator, G. (Communications Design, KNUST, Ghana)</p> <p>Agyei, E. T. (Indigenous Art and Technology, KNUST, Ghana)</p> <p>Appiah, S. P. (Chemistry, KNUST, Ghana)</p> <p>Fening, P. A. (Industrial Art, KNUST, Ghana)</p>	<p>Ali Dansieh, S. (Dr. Hilla Limann Technical University, Ghana)</p> <p>Adu-Mensah, J. (University of Cape Coast, Ghana)</p> <p>Yarney, L. (University of Ghana, Ghana)</p> <p>Owusu, E. K. (College of Health and Wellbeing, Ghana)</p> <p>Manu, G. (Sunyani Technical University, Ghana)</p> <p>Brewu, J. (Akrokkeri College of Education, Ghana)</p> <p>Addo, I. A. (University of Ghana, Ghana)</p> <p>Wemegah, I. (Akenten Appiah-Menka University, Ghana)</p> <p>Tetteh, N. A. (Dr. Hilla Limann Technical University, Ghana)</p>	<p>Boamah, D. A. (Queens University, Canada)</p> <p>Chukwuere, J. (Northwest University, South Africa)</p> <p>Aravind, V. R. (Clarion University, United States)</p> <p>Ferdinand-James, D. S. (University of West Indies, Jamaica)</p> <p>Aslan, I. (Bingol University, Bingol, Turkey)</p> <p>Corte, V. (University of Naples, Napoli, Italy)</p> <p>Periasamy, A. (Madras School of Social Work, Tamil Nadu, India)</p> <p>Krishnappa, M. K. (University of Tamil Nadu, India)</p> <p>Gouthami, V. (KAHM Unity Women's College, India)</p> <p>Amitha B. K. H. (Kerala Forest Institute, India)</p>

<p>KNUST, Ghana)</p>	<p>Glover, R. (Publishing Studies, KNUST, Ghana)</p> <p>Bodjawah, E. (Painting & Sculpture, KNUST, Ghana)</p> <p>Daitey, S. T. (Indigenous Arts and Technology, KNUST, Ghana)</p> <p>Agyei, I. (Industrial Art, KNUST, Ghana)</p> <p>Asamoah, S. P. (Painting & Sculpture, KNUST, Ghana)</p> <p>Padditey, E. (Indigenous Arts and Technology, KNUST, Ghana)</p> <p>Twene, A. (Publishing Studies, KNUST, Ghana)</p>	<p>Akpem, B. (Dr. Hilla Limann Technical University, Ghana)</p> <p>Agbezuge, M. A. (Akenten Appiah-Menka University, Ghana)</p> <p>Danso, D.K. (Akenten Appiah-Menka University, Ghana)</p>	<p>Aneesh, C. (Kerala Forest Institute, India)</p> <p>Krishnamurthy, S. (The Roots, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India)</p> <p>Mohammed, A. (Universiti Malaysia, Malaysia)</p> <p>Said, M. (Imam Bukhari International Scientific-Research Center, Uzbekistan)</p> <p>Saravanan, P. (Madras Medical College, India)</p> <p>Del Gaudio, G. (University of Naples, Italy)</p> <p>Nevola, G. (University of Naples, Italy)</p> <p>Hanchate, D. (Institute of Engineering and Technology, India)</p> <p>Umachandran, K. (Nelcast Ltd., India)</p> <p>Ziarati, P. (Islamic Azad University, Iran)</p> <p>Behmanesh, M. (Tarbiat Modares University, Iran)</p> <p>Skiba, D. (University of Life Sciences, Poland)</p> <p>Thulla, P.F.Y. (Njala University,</p>
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			<p>Sierra Leone)</p> <p>Moriba, S. (Freetown Polytechnic, Sierra Leone)</p> <p>Mensah-Gborie, M.N.S. (Njala University, Sierra Leone)</p> <p>Sawicka, B. (University of Life Sciences, Lublin, Poland)</p> <p>Adetunji, C. O. (Edo State University, Nigeria)</p> <p>Egbuna, C. (IPS Intelligentsia Publishing Services, Nigeria)</p> <p>Tijani, H. (Bauchi State University, Nigeria)</p> <p>Panda, P. (Sri Sri University, India)</p> <p>Padmanaban, S. (University of Bologna, Italy)</p> <p>Subudhi, C. (Central University of Tamil Nadu, India)</p> <p>Sharma, E. (Ahmedabad University, India)</p> <p>Sharma, S. (Ahmedabad University, India)</p> <p>Abdolresa, R. F. (Islamic Azad University, Iran)</p> <p>Sajjadi, J. (Islamic Azad University, Iran)</p>
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			Dimitros, V. (Erasmus University, Rotterdam, Netherlands)
			Sedighi, S. (Islamic Azad University, Iran)
8	16	12	38

Total number of collaborations: **74**

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF

1. Research Journal of Advanced Humanities (Royallite Global Inc.), Kenya, Since May 23, 2020
2. Journal of African Culture, History and Arts (JFP Publishers), South Africa, Since October 1, 2021

ASSOCIATE EDITOR

1. Frontiers in Human Dynamics (Environment, Politics and Society)

GUEST/ACADEMIC/ARTICLE EDITOR

1. SAGE Open- Since December 2021
2. Art and Design Review- Since January 2022
3. Asian Journal of Language, Literature and Cultural Studies
4. Journal of Geography, Environment and Earth Science International

EDITORIAL BOARD MEMBER

1. Journal of African Art Education
2. Journal of Sociology and Anthropology
3. ASEAN Multidisciplinary Research Journal
4. ASEAN Journal of Basic and Higher Education
5. Global Journal of Science Frontier Research
6. African Social Science and Humanities Journal

PEER REVIEW ACTIVITY FOR ACADEMIC JOURNALS

(289 PEER REVIEWED ARTICLES FROM 2019-2022)

<https://publons.com/researcher/1316663/dr-dickson-adom/>

<https://www.webofscience.com/wos/author/record/J-7934-2016>

WORKSHOPS ATTENDED

1. Research Academy on Campus- SciVal: All about reporting! (Elsevier Publishing) – 19th November, 2020
2. Quality Assurance in Higher & Tertiary Education Workshop, (July-October, 2020), Association of African Universities (AAU)
3. African Humanities Program (AHP) Proposal Writing Workshop, KANAC, 5th–6th November, 2020
4. Research Academy on Campus- SciVal: Analysing research contributions toward the UN Sustainable Development Goals! (Elsevier Publishing) – 12th November, 2020
5. Online COVID-19 Sensitization, Karatina University, December 18, 2020
6. Get Ready to Publish a Book, Emerald Publishing, September 29, 2020
7. Workshop on Employability (8th and 9th October, 2021). University of Liezig, Germany.
8. Research Academy on Campus- SciVal: What's new and coming soon? (Elsevier Publishing) – 3rd November, 2020
9. Kudos and De Gruyter Materclass: Effective dissemination to optimize reach and visibility for your research, October 22 2019, Kudos and De Gruyter
10. Kudos and Brill Materclass: How to promote your work, December 10, 2019, Kudos and Brill

CERTIFIED INSTITUTIONAL SHORT COURSES

1. Pyramids of Giza: Ancient Egyptian Art and Archaeology (Harvard University), May 10- September 20, 2020.
2. Facilitating Online, University of Cape Town, September 7- November 8, 2020
3. AfricaLive! Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies (Harvard University Executive Education), January 11, 2021- February 20, 2021
4. Editorial Workflow in OJS 3, Simon Fraser University, March 4, 2021- June 8, 2021
5. Digital Teaching and Learning Course (Certified Associate in Digital Teaching and Learning)- September 2- September 14, 2020- Ghana Society for Education Technology
6. Access to Research for Development and Innovation: ARDI (Grade: 85.42%), Research4Life (United Nations Technology Bank for Least Developed Countries, UN TBLDC)- October 5- November 8, 2020
7. Quantitative Analysis Training (EV Excelledia Ventures Digital Innovations), 15th February, 2021- 3rd March, 2021
8. Faculty Development Program on Multivariate Data Analysis- JVA EduTech, November 16- November 22, 2020
9. KNUST Online Teaching Training Course, September 2020, KNUST
10. African Art. E-Learning course, FPLI-Academia Luso Italiana, Lda, Italy, December, 2021.
11. Access to Research for Development and Innovation: ARDI. Research4Life Massive Open Online Course. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, United Nations Technology Bank for Least Developed Countries, October, 2020.

NATIONAL AND INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES ATTENDED

1. 35th World Congress of Art History CIHA (International Committee of Art History), Sao Paulo, Brazil, 17-21 January 2022
2. International conference on management of COVID-19 (Ali Allana College of Pharmacy, Akkalkuwa)- 27th – 29th June, 2020
3. International conference on COVID-19 Global Impacts (African-British Journals), 20-21 July, 2020
4. International Conference on Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration (Brussels, Belgium) May 15th-16th, 2019.
5. The 18th Urban Research Plaza’s Forum “*Art and Cultural Activities with Covid-19*” and “*Saving Our Urban Habitat – Creating A Sustainable Future*” 8th – 9th March, 2021, Chulalongkom University, Thailand and the Urban Research Plaza, Osaka City University, Japan.
6. International Conference on Art and Science. Webinar invitation. 26th – 28th January, 2021.
7. First conference on Employability. “Work and Economic Futures. (Africa and beyond)” 23rd April, 2021. University of Liepzig, Germany.
8. ACCESS Research Pillar’s presentation on the progress report of short-term scholarships in K.N.U.S.T. University of Liepzig, Germany. 22nd February, 2021.
9. The 3rd International Ethics Congress. 10th – 11th October, 2021. Ankara Turkey.
10. The Papyrus Boot Camp “writing a Peer a Review based from the standards of Web of Science” 12th December, 2021.
11. The 2nd VAMCON (Virtual AEAN Multidisciplinary Research Conference 2021) Conference Session Chair. November 6th -7th, 2021. Pangasinan, Philippines.
12. The 2nd VAMCON (Virtual AEAN Multidisciplinary Research Conference 2021). Plenary Speaker “Theoretical and Conceptual Framework and its Relevance to Quality Research” November 6th -7th, 2021. Pangasinan, Philippines.

EXHIBITIONS

- Curated an Art Exhibition titled “A part of my journey’, Artist: Samuel Prophask Asamoah, Centre for National Culture (Arts Centre Gallery, Accra.) 4th -31st December 2021.

REFEREES

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 TECHNOLOGY
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